

Twin Occlusion Prosthesis: A Case Report

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Abstract

Hemimandibulectomy patient presents with many debilitating problems because of deviation of mandible on affected side. This incapacitation depends upon the amount of hard and soft tissue resected, remaining dentition and tongue mobility for mastication and other oral functions. It is essential to restore the oral function like mastication in such patients to ensure for an ability to have healthy diet and overall general health. The treatment options for such patients are surgical restoration of resected part, physiotherapy or prosthodontic intervention. Prosthodontic options are to either provide guiding flange prosthesis or twin occlusion prosthesis. Appropriate treatment option is to be chosen depending upon the degree of loss of structure and function. This article presents a technique of restoring oral function for a hemimandibulectomy patient by twin occlusion prosthesis.

Key Words: Twin Occlusion Prosthesis, Hemimandibulectomy.

Introduction

Mandibular deviation is multifactorial defect and its severity is based on the extent of osseous and soft tissue involvement, degree of tongue impaired, the loss of sensory and motor innervations, the type of wound closure, the presence of remaining natural teeth and finally the first initiation of prosthetic treatment¹.

Oral diseases are widespread all over the world and negatively affect people's quality of life. It greatly affects various anatomic regions of the oral cavity, making the functions like chewing, swallowing, speech, and oral competence difficult².

These include ameloblastoma, osteoradionecrosis of jaws, salivary gland tumors, oropharyngeal carcinomas, trauma, and so on. However, the most frequent carcinomas in the head and neck area are squamous cell carcinomas of the oral cavity³.

Squamous cell carcinoma of the oral cavity is a malignant neoplasm that makes individuals suffer both physiologically and psychologically. Surgical resection of the tumor and the structures involved with it, along with radiotherapy or chemotherapy, is the treatment protocol for oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC)⁴.

One of the most difficult and demanding essays is the prosthodontic rehabilitation

of such individuals, especially for the mandible, because the segmental loss of mandibular integrity leads to its deviation towards the resected area with lack of occlusion. In addition, segmental loss of mandible results in limited mouth opening, scar formation, abnormal jaw relationships, and compromised health of oral mucosa which further worsens the mandibular deviation to reestablish an acceptable occlusal relationship for the residual dentition which helps to achieve mastication is the mainstay treatment modality for hemimandibulectomy cases^{5,6,7}.

This study will help the viewers in dealing with the treatment plan of the patients undergoing hemi-mandibulectomy, and it will lend a helping hand to postgraduate trainees in constructing a maxillary partial denture with a double occlusal table. The goal of this article is to present a prosthesis that is simple, lightweight yet strong enough to withstand the masticatory forces, and cost-effective as patients with oral carcinomas are mostly from a low socioeconomic background, due to the consumption of chewing and smoking carcinogens.

Case Report

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A 58 year old Female patient reported to the Department of Prosthodontics with a chief complaint of difficulty in mastication since 6 months. Her medical history revealed that she was diagnosed for squamous cell carcinoma on the left side of the mandible, for which she had undergone extensive resection of the entire mandible on left half of the mandible 3 years back. An extra oral examination showed asymmetrical face, and a convex profile. There was deviation of the mandible to the left side that is towards the resected side.

Pre Operative

Clinical Procedure

Preliminary impressions were made with irreversible hydrocolloid material using stock trays and casts were poured with type III dental stone. On the maxillary cast a custom tray was fabricated with self-cure acrylic resin (RR, Dentsply, India). Impressions were poured with type III dental stone to obtain a final cast. Denture base was fabricated and wax occlusal bit was made. Maxillary master cast was articulated using a Mean value articulator. Maxillomandibular relations were recorded with Modell-ing wax to get interocclusal records.

Twin Occlusion On Cast

The patient was advised to move his mandible as far as possible to the untreated side and then gently close his mandibular jaw into position to record a functional maxillomandibular relationship. After articulation, one set of anatomic teeth were selected

Twin Occlusion In Mouth-post Insertion

Post Insertion Twin Occlusion

Discussion

Olson ML et al⁸ in 1978 and Curtis DA et al⁹ in 1997 recommended that immediate reconstruction of resected part of mandible should be done to recover both facial symmetry and masticatory function.

Classes	Description
Class 1	Mandibular resection involving alveolar defect with preservation of mandibular continuity.
Class 2	Resection defects involve loss of mandibular continuity distal to the canine area.
Class 3	Resection defect involves loss up to the mandibular midline region.
Class 4	Resection defect involves the lateral aspect of the mandible, but are augmented to maintain pseudo articulation of bone and soft tissues in the region of the ascending ramus.
Class 5	Resection defect involves the symphysis and parasymphysis region only, augmented to preserve bilateral temporomandibular articulations.
Class 6	Similar to class V, except that the mandibular continuity is not restored.

Table: 01 Cantor and Curtis classification for Hemi mandibulectomy

It is reported that even the recent developments in reconstructive surgery and prosthodontic rehabilitation have not been able to restore impaired masticatory function in 50% of head and neck cancer patients. Osseointegrated dental implants provide a treatment modality that may adequately rehabilitate oral functions of these patients so that they can lead a healthy life. However this is an expensive modality which may be not be acceptable to all strata of patients. In this case the guidance prosthesis was not planned because a time period of 3 years had elapsed and scar tissue

formation had occurred.^{10,11,12} Twin occlusion was provided because the patient could not occlude on the natural teeth. The palatal row of teeth occluded with the remaining natural mandibular teeth and the buccal row of natural teeth supported the cheeks. This technique enables the patient to masticate appropriately, to lead a healthy, good quality of life. It helps patient to deal with the physical and psychological disabilities.

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